

Formation Constants of 3-Nitrosalicylate Complexes of Copper (II), Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II)

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Potentiometric study showed the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes between copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) and 3-nitrosalicylic acid (3NSA). The formation constants of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes have been determined by employing Bjerrum's method¹. The order of stability is found to be $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co}$, which is in accordance with Irving-William rule².

A survey of literature shows no reference of the formation of 3NSA complexes with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} . The present investigations deal with the same.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were of either B.D.H. 'AnalaR' or equivalent quality.

Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salts were prepared in double-distilled water.

pH of the solutions was measured by using 'Polymetron CL-41' pH-meter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bjerrum's pH-titration technique¹ was adopted for obtaining the stepwise stability constants of the complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 3NSA. Since the reagent was insoluble in water, a 25-75 (v/v) water-dioxane solvent was used. A bulk electrolyte of μ 0.1M sodium perchlorate was adopted to maintain the constant ionic strength and reaction solutions were all thermostated at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

In calculating the values of \bar{n} and $[\text{A}^{2-}]$, the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration. In this way a series of values of \bar{n} and $[\text{A}^{2-}]$, corresponding to different values of pH were obtained in each case.

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Formation curves were obtained by plotting \bar{n} against $[A^{2-}]$ as given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ for copper-, nickel-, and cobalt-3-nitrosalicylates were directly read from their formation curves. These have been given in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Formation constants and fundamental properties of 3-nitrosalicylates.

TABLE 1

Stabilities of Metal Chelates of 3-Nitrosalicylic Acid

Metal	At No.	2nd I.P.	Electro-negativity	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Cu	29	20.34	1.75	7.72	7.25	14.97
Ni	28	18.20	1.75	6.22	6.00	12.32
Co	27	17.30	1.70	5.65	5.30	10.95

Table 1 indicates that $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ values of 3-nitrosalicylates follow the order Copper > Nickel > Cobalt which is in accordance with Irving-William².

A parallelism between $\log K_n$ and 2nd I.P. is obtained in the present case also as has been earlier pointed out by Irving and William². Except for zinc, this potential measures the energy required for the removal of a 'd'-electron showing the involvement of 'd' orbitals in the chelation.

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